

Building a multi-surround system on the spot with our phones

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ABSTRACT

This demo will demonstrate my project to synchronize mobile devices with each other to play the same song together simultaneously. Guests can give it a try to participate with their mobile device in a collaborative audio playback session, to build our own multi-surround system live. I will have my laptop setup to provide the host device, so everyone can connect as a player. Participants are expected to be physically present on-site. Remote attendees participating via an online stream, which in theory could be possible to partake, may be problematic due to drifting connection speeds.

1. PROTOTYPE STATUS

The web-application is in continuous development. Depending on the progress, some of the techniques mentioned in the talk may or may not have been adopted in the deployed prototype, which influences the user experience and the range of supported devices. We are there to assist with getting your device in sync and are really excited to see how well everything connects.

2. REQUIREMENTS

It requires an active internet connection, one device with a proper GPU and an internal/external microphone, and ideally multiple phones which have somewhat up-to-date web-browsers installed. External output devices, which suffer from high output latencies, e.g. Bluetooth speakers, should be applicable to use as a valid output target. Any device that wants to sync requires to be perceivable by the host microphone.

3. ONLINE AVAILABLE

The website is reachable online at sync.jervtub.com. Note: to try it out, it requires a proper host device, which can be problematic, since the GPU code is unstable which "just works on my device". This part of the development requires significant improvements on device support. Therefore the on-site demo is a convenient moment to give it a try without having to run into such problem.

4. FURTHER INFORMATION

Further information about the prototype and its design choices, including the algorithms and code dependencies used, can be found in the documentation of the GitHub repository [2].

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Prior prototype of my bachelor thesis [3], and the GPU-accelerated cross-correlation tool [1]. Thanks to Leiden University and Utrecht University for providing the courses Human Computer Interaction and Optimization and Vectorization respectively, which helped me significantly in the development history. The available Web Audio API documentation, the previously published WebAudioConf material that gave inspiration and knowledge on several parts, the original creators of the AudioModem application for inspiration on using high-frequency signals.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Github repository of gpu-accelerated repo. <https://github.com/jervtub/audiosignal-correlation>. Last accessed: 2022-04-15.
- [2] Github repository of the prototype. <https://github.com/jervtub/sync>. Last accessed: 2022-04-15.
- [3] J. van Tubergen. Assessing the fitness of web-applications within the context of mobile phones, on performing spatially distributed, co-located, collaborative, audio-related activities. 2020.

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